

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ON THE NECESSITY OF MAKING AMENDMENTS TO THE EU FOOD SECURITY POLICY ON THE EXAMPLE OF ROMANIA

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of the current situation of EU food security policy. The traditional agricultural sector in Romania are forced to move into other areas of activity due to the unprofitability of the agricultural business.

Keywords: food security policy, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, problem of implementing the EU Common Agricultural Policy, European Union.

After the crisis of the 1970s, the term “food security” began to “take shape” and was introduced into the official lexicon. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has become the main source of the establishment an international cooperation in this area. Currently, the term “food security” includes four fundamental components: availability, accessibility, utilization and stability. The researchers concluded that when speaking about food security first of all it means the need to identify shortcomings and negative factors that influence the development of an appropriate food policy.

Food production includes the process of processing, distribution, trade and consumption. It is well known that military conflict is a driving force behind world hunger, and food insecurity is often used as a weapon.[1] As a result, negative factors (military operations, natural disasters, destruction of infrastructure) lead to limited access to agricultural goods and changes in prices for agricultural products.

Economists note that prices for agricultural products have been steadily rising since 2020. Scientists highlight the COVID-19 pandemic and the military crisis in Ukraine as negative factors that influenced this process. As a result, in March 2022, the European Union adopted a resolution on the need for an immediate plan of actions to ensure food security within the region. At the same time, a number of experts argue that the steps taken by Brussels do not fully correspond to the interests of all EU countries. Regional policy levers that correspond to the traditional foundations of the European Union member states are still needed.

At the same time, a number of researchers focus on the problem of implementing the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).[2] The CAP is a set of legislative instruments that provide farmers with income generation support, market assessment and rural development with the aim of preserving rural landscapes and the environment while increasing agricultural production. However, the general policy is not always applicable to all member countries of the alliance.

In particular, Romania remains the main exporter of wheat from the EU and is among the top five countries with a grain surplus (France, Romania, Bulgaria,

Germany, Poland). According to the leaders of Romania, the country plans to harvest from 10.09 million to 11.15 million tons of wheat in 2025, increasing the sown area by 120 thousand hectares – to 2.3 million hectares. At the same time, the wheat yield is predicted to be at the level of previous years - 4.62 tons/ha.

It is worth noting that the export of the specified raw materials in 2023-2024 amounted to 37 million tons. The main importing countries are China, Algeria, Morocco and Egypt. According to statistics the domestic consumption of wheat by the Romanian population is 2.5-3 million tons per year. This creates a surplus of 7 million tons for export which could make a significant contribution to the country's economy.

The main problematic aspect for Romanian farmers remains the export of cheap grain from Ukraine via Romania. Taking into account the existing warehouses and food resources on the territory of Romania, the majority of imported grain is accumulated here. This circumstance is the result of Brussels' policy aimed at supporting the Ukrainian side. Thus, in 2024, about 1 million tons of wheat were exported to Romania at dumping prices.

At the same time, the EU is making attempts to mitigate the corresponding risks. The proposals outlined in the EPRS studies and the TFEU treaties were put forward as priority steps.[3] These structures are called upon to develop not only food security, but also to serve the benefit of the EU economy.

However, in 2024, in the international tender of the Egyptian State Agency for Food Purchasing (GASC) wheat from Romania was offered at a historically low price of \$294.99 per ton. This indicator is of interest to real estate companies that resell grain, but not to farmers interested in agricultural development. Thus, the development of new land plots requires expenses on equipment, maintenance, fuel, fertilizers, workers' salaries, etc. The beginning of the sowing season for a farmer begins with credit obligations. Accordingly, the question arises about the business feasibility in conditions of unprofitability. This creates unfavorable prospects for the Romanian farmer. We assume that 2025 is marked by the breakdown of the European development program from “farm to fork” (adopted by

the EU). More and more representatives of the traditional agricultural sector in Romania are forced to move into other areas of activity due to the unprofitability of the agricultural business.

Thus, in order to ensure stability and development of the European Union, it is necessary to focus on traditional sectors of the economy. Agriculture remains a priority area requiring adjustments from Brussels. Thus, the candidate for the post of President of Romania, Calin Georgescu, at the end of 2024 proposed a strategic plan that includes a ban on the export of Ukrainian grain through Romania. According to the politician, this measure is a priority for the development of his country for the benefit of the EU.

References

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